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Pandemic Data Circulation

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Introduction

We have been two years in the pandemic, and many interesting patterns have emerged that are worth discussing. I can only attempt to touch on a few of them, which are related to the practices and flows of health data. It was interesting to see, as the pandemic ensued, how lots of different kinds of data were mobilised. And lots of different social actors got involved in the use of data, for many different purposes. Data were put in circulation in ways and speed that were unforeseen, from both public and private sector companies. But data circulate well in some directions, and less so in others. Overwhelmed perusing a constantly moving panoply of numbers, charts and assessments on the state of the pandemic, it is easy to miss out that some data are not flowing well at all, and that others should perhaps stay where they are.

UK: ‘State of play’

The UK has been widely regarded as one country where the state has been most willing to play with various sorts of data experimentation. A report by the Alan Turing Institute on data science and artificial intelligence in the ‘age’ of covid (von Borzyskowski et al. 2021) highlights how, in many ways, the pandemic was an exceptionally propitious opportunity for all sorts of innovation and experimentation with data to occur. As it started reacting to the C19 outbreak, on 17th March 2020 the

Government mandated healthcare data custodians at NHS Digital to support access and processing of health data by authorised organisations for purposes of pandemic response (Secretary of State for Health and Social Care 2020). The relaxation of regulatory standards, with a mandate for various public agencies to put the data in motion, was the first ‘booster’ for the circulation of data. But it was not only national healthcare system data that were quickly mobilised. Private companies including the likes of Silicon Valley giants Google and Apple also offered select access to proprietary data, albeit to a limited extent.

This created the space for various teams and organisations to intervene and offer their services as to how such an unprecedented and all-encompassing mobilisation could be achieved. Datasets that could matter for the coordination of response were myriad, as were the indicators to closely watch to monitor how things unfold. Government decision makers procured from private companies a set of analytics computational infrastructures to manage the first, and analytics dashboards for watching the second. One of the most important contracts, worth more than 12.5 million GBP (Gov.UK 2020), was awarded to Palantir – a secretive Silicon Valley company familiar to controversies thanks to its propensity sourcing contracts from military, intelligence and border control agencies involved in politically questionable missions. Consultancies McKinsey, Deloitte and Faculty AI also contributed.

On top of Palantir’s computational infrastructure NHS Digital could then launch a ‘COVID-19 Data Store’, a repository of datasets available to agencies involved in the pandemic response: *“NHS COVID-19 Data Store brings together and protects accurate, real-time information to inform strategic and operational decisions in response to the current pandemic in one place.”* (NHS England 2022a) The datasets included in the Data Store are rather disparate and come in many different formats, as a collection which could be potentially accessed by many different users for many different purposes would be (NHS England 2022b). There are data such as raw NHS medical helpline call data; NHS staff absence reports; mobility data from Google and Apple; ERP data for healthcare system management; patient demographics; counts of online and video consultations; personal protective equipment stocks and purchases; and even self-report symptom data collected by volunteers for the Covid Symptom Study using the citizen science app developed by Zoe, a company. These data are not limited to tables of numerical and/or structured text values. They are also *lists; lookup tables; summaries of historical data; records that ‘describe’*.

Thanks to several dashboards and analytics features which draw disparate data sources together in ‘actionable’ summaries of visualisations, charts and numbers, decision makers in government should be equipped with the best real time intelligence to take complex decisions: *“These dashboards are designed to help senior national and regional officials to make policy and strategic decisions in response to Covid-19”* (NHS England 2022a). Perusing Palantir’s contract we learn that the system comprises of three main interfaces: the Strategic Decision Makers Dashboard; Recovery of Critical Services; and Early Warning System. We also learn that these technologies might have a scope and longevity that reach farer than the pandemic alone: they should help to *“coordinate national response to COVID-19 and EU Exit”* and provisions are made to allow the Government to transition this system from the pandemic use to

“general business-as-usual monitoring” (if Palantir’s software-as-a-service contract is renewed past expiry). The Early Warning System interface seems the most ambitious, sporting an *“Explainability and Trust Overview”* feature displaying forecasts generated by the models of a private third party (the consultancy Faculty AI, founded by a physicist) using NHS data, 111 medical helpline data, and Google and Apple mobility data among others. And so, the time when governing comes to resemble a session of Sim City (or Chile’s CyberSyn room of cybernetic government, captured by Medina 2015) might be finally here. Those who sit at the fence of government action and have limited information to go by might have many questions about this ‘system of systems’. One may wonder, for instance, who is interested in knowing counts of tele-care consultations? How many of the people calling a medical helpline or logging their symptoms through the ZOE app would imagine that their data could show up on a government dashboard, and what would they think if they knew? Are self-report data from the ZOE app displayed on any dashboard, and who looks at it?

Those around the Data Store are not the only movements of health data between public and private sector that are currently noteworthy in the UK. The GP Data for Planning and Research (n.b. GDPR – not GDPR) is a policy unveiled in the Spring of 2021 that, resurrecting the ambitions of defunct *care.data* framework (Vezyridis and Timmons 2017), mandates NHS Digital to create a centralised repository of general practitioner healthcare data, the access to which should be sold to private sector companies on a cost-recovery basis. It is the latest of a series of attempts to enable the permanent circulation of national healthcare system data in the UK private sector and boost its valorisation. As researchers at the Ada Lovelace Institute observe (Machirori and Patel 2021), the scheme was introduced with notable disregard for public engagement through a ‘method’ that could be described as ‘decide, announce and defend’: if the policy is rammed through fast enough, it might survive the public backlash and the government would get its way. Once again, public backlash might prove sticky enough. The introduction of the plan has been delayed and there has been a sizeable opt-out, as noted by Cori Crider, director of Foxglove Legal, in a recent expert consultation by the Ada Lovelace Institute (2021). Regardless the exact timings, the repeated attempts of consecutive UK governments to enable private sector use of patient records demonstrate a long-term determination, which predates and will outlast the pandemic, to get health data to circulate more widely and loosely and for many more purposes than the performance of health care; and for the government to allow private data platform developers to embed themselves in the infrastructure of the state and its governance activity. As also highlighted by the Ada Lovelace Institute, the UK Government fancies the opportunity to turn the relaxation of data circulation regulations introduced during the pandemic into a standard for the future regulatory regime, so as to favour faster and broader circulation.

The same kind of pattern has been observed in yet another front of government development of pandemic technology infrastructure, that of contact-tracing apps. As Rob Kitchin has noted (Kitchin 2020), in order to develop contact-tracing apps many countries desperate to curb the spread of C19 resorted to working with organisations that have been at the centre of scandals or polemics in ‘normal’ time because they develop controversial techniques, technologies or services of population surveillance. Contact-tracing collaborations includes organisations such as NSO Group, who sells

weapons-grade spyware to illiberal and autocratic governments accused of repressing dissidents and opponents, and has worked with Israel on their app. More notoriously, tech giants and mobile monopolists Google and Apple, who rushed to offer a common Bluetooth-based stack for automating contact tracing in Android and iOS phones, used their privileged position of mobile gatekeepers to make an impactful contribution (not without privacy implications – see Kitchin 2020).

Translating private technology to public infrastructure

In respect to organisational operations and decisions, data seem to circulate well indeed. Many more private organisations have been taking part in the covid data craze, often with much display aimed at ‘covid-washing’ their reputation (Kitchin 2020), keen to be seen as generous tech wizards rather than greedy data harvesters. After all, one might say, there is a point in letting these companies collect so much data about the public, if they respond to the call when their help is needed. But it is in particular those organisations who outside of ‘pandemic time’ have been at the centre of many ethical controversies over the ways in which they generate and use data that have rushed to the forefront of more and less consequential efforts to help. It reveals a key assumption as to the ways in which technological, organisational and methodological frameworks originally developed for watching and manipulating consumer behaviour through digital technology have been seen as *translatable* to the context of social distancing restrictions and other emergency rules. The double-edgedness of these initiatives is easy to surmise. For instance, data broker Experian, who sells individual data at population scale after collecting them through a vast network of business relationships and repackaging them in the form of value-added marketing demographics, studied the distribution of Covid’s socio-economic impacts. Besides the potential to help public health response, one should remember the knowledge thus generated is likely to have value for marketing demographics too; and so, the first beneficiary of this effort might well be Experian itself. At least in a rhetorical sense, these frameworks have proved translatable: research into individual attitudes towards contact-tracing apps (Lucivero et al. 2021) shows that many believe the impact of intensive data collection and cross-dataset linking is negligible since the lives of ordinary individuals are already intensively surveilled, and for much less of a reason.

With so much ‘help’ on offer, the pandemic has certainly reaffirmed the central role of private technology in the coordination of society’s reaction to emerging events. But should it? A piece on the Harvard Business Review (Balsari, Buckee, and Khanna 2020) suggests otherwise. A “*tidal wave of data*” is sloshing around all corners, but not much of it might be “*any good*”. Many datasets made available are incomplete in ways that are not-randomly distributed across society, but rather, reflect socio-economic inequalities. If the disadvantaged are less well represented in datasets used to coordinate pandemic response, expect the inequality to be drawn on. And so, the authors suggest, while many tech organisations are busy offering up datasets and

expertise on linkage, hosting and analytics, there is not enough engagement with subject matter experts; many models are produced with expertise that is translated from being involved in the solution of problems other than the medical, but rather, rooted in mathematics, physics, or operations management expertise, among others; other innovations, such as automated contact-tracing, are live experiments. What a contrast with the exhortations of data analytics and visualisations leader Tableau, who encourages users to start *“your own analysis”* (Tableau 2022). Cloud-computing giant, Amazon Web Services, offers a suite of data and computational infrastructure resources to help and *“provide these experts with the data and tools needed to better understand, track, plan for, and eventually contain and neutralize the virus that causes COVID-19”* (Amazon Web Services 2020). Experts can *“use AWS or third-party tools to perform trend analysis, do keyword search, perform question/answer analysis, build and run machine learning models, or run custom analyses to meet their specific needs.”*

The challenges that remain

While some data might have been circulated in and out, and across, government quite well, other data were not circulating equally well. As the Alan Turing Institute’s report observes (von Borzyskowski et al. 2021), a number of challenges were experienced by the community of data science and artificial intelligence researchers striving to make an impact through the production of new knowledge about Covid-19. Certain kinds of data can be difficult to access because of governance issues – the Ada Lovelace Institute points out that current governance processes were often too slow and required too much of too few data custodians (Ada Lovelace Institute 2021) – but also because they are more difficult to generate than others. Data on some pandemic response measures and their impacts, such as non-pharmaceutical interventions (e.g. social distancing and face masks), were not sufficiently available. Local council and administration decision makers complained not enough data were made available to them. Uneven quality and representation in population datasets further raised concerns of inequality in the response to the pandemic. Unequal vulnerability to pandemic response measures would also lead to mistrust and uneven participation and compliance in various undertakings, such as active installs of contact-tracing apps, or symptom self-reporting in citizen science studies such as ZOE’s. While datasets were over-produced in a scramble to help, attention slipped over quality and methodological issues such as sampling (von Borzyskowski et al. 2021). While new problems are often resolved more quickly the more open and participative is the search for a solution, there is a way in which the eventually ensuing chaos brings about new problems in the meantime. The ubiquitous discussion of statistics and data in all kinds of public reporting further amplified concerns over interpretation and communication. Last but not least, Alan Turing Institute researchers complain about their relationship with government decision makers. They found it difficult to understand if the expert knowledge that they were generating through many studies was getting any attention by policy makers. Researchers who are well connected could have government’s ear and access data that others could not. As we have seen, government decision-makers were providing themselves with cutting-edge analytics

technology from private firms the likes of Palantir. It is as if they wanted to lock themselves up in the button room with the latest tech gear, leaving other experts outside who kept insisting they could help. The appeal of translating all-powerful consumer surveillance infrastructure might have been more powerful than working with experts the old way.

From normal to pandemic time, and back

From this quick sketch, it should be possible to get a feel for a complex and protracted situation involving many kinds of initiatives, data practices, actions, claims, and contexts of use. Talk about data can be at different levels (Tempini 2020; Leonelli 2016; Rosenberg 2013) – as digital object stored on computer systems, as epistemic product of an empirical scientific investigation or of activist projects, and as a rhetorical device that can be waved around (as in the press conferences that saw Boris Johnson so frequently argue that the UK government ‘just’ followed the data). This makes the analysis of data practices and movements complex. Some of the stakes of data practices and movements from ‘pandemic time’ will be played out in the future, and in such a cacophony of data practices and claims it is easy to lose sight of a few big trends that have been driving all things data. But there is perhaps enough to see that the circulation of data during the pandemic was uneven and dependent on many factors including the organisational and technological infrastructures datasets are managed with; and to suspect that the pandemic crisis, like many other crises, won’t be let go to waste, and instead, will allow private infrastructure to be wedged further underneath society and its spaces. In times of emergency a general mobilisation of all sectors and actors might feel like the only intelligent thing to do, and so many private sector organisations all scrambled to see what they could offer to government and research community. But in all things infrastructural, there is a strong sense in which the past will become the present, and the present will become the future; because infrastructures are built over long time and sit on top of even longer-evolving methodological and cultural frames, path dependencies are deemed and continued through the material shaping of systems and practices (Bowker and Star 1999; Star and Ruhleder 1996; Hanseth, Monteiro, and Hatling 1996; Hanseth 1996).

Time was of the essence, and the rapidity with which private data-intensive businesses deployed a panoply of initiatives to share and analyse data of all kinds bears witness to the strategic dynamism and translatability of data platforms. Response to the pandemic was characterised by lack of time, and those who control data infrastructures were in a good position to enter the frame of pandemic response efforts and reap financial and reputational benefits. Infrastructure evolution in ‘normal’ time has often been seen as challenged by ‘infrastructural inertia’ (Bowker and Star 1999; Star and Ruhleder 1996) – the way in which infrastructures swamp change and make material legacy. In ‘pandemic time’, instead, it seems as if infrastructures were key to enable movement and change. All time had been suddenly sucked out. Being able to re-deploy and re-purpose data infrastructures and methods was a chief way to buy time. This might not need to be a contradiction. Infrastructural inertia is likely to be observed as an infrastructural reaction when the change that is being carried out is proactive or transformative – a move away from the current ways of doing. The change and re-organisation that the *pandemic time* required was essentially *reactive* – when surprised and unprepared to unexpected developments, the current ways of doing might be the only available to effect change. Infrastructures and methods that are re-deployable, transferable and extendable are quickly whisked into new positions.

One could wonder why should we be concerned about all this? That is because once time is 'normal' again, infrastructural inertia can kick in again. Dislodging private technology infrastructure, and the practices associated with it, that was deeply embedded in the government machinery back in pandemic time will become ever more difficult. As Sharon points out (Sharon 2020), running pandemic response with the technology provided by private corporations will "increase our dependency on them for the provision of (public) services, and they make themselves necessary passage points for the adequate functioning of these sectors" in the future. Continued reliance on any infrastructure makes it invisible and undermines the imagination of technological-organisational-political alignments that respond to different values, priorities and logics. Complex and consequential infrastructures and their developmental inertia help to make the past that they came from before the pandemic to continue through and after it and reveal some of the linkages that keep the socio-technical before-during-after of pandemics threaded together.

Update 9th June 2022

This morning the Financial Times is breaking with reporting suggesting the Government is planning to award a giant contract for the provision of a data analytics "operating system for the NHS" and Palantir is devoting enormous resources to win the contract. Privacy activists who have exposed Palantir's penetration in state infrastructure since 2021 point out the same kinds of concerns I have been repeating here. It turns out worrying developments might be moving even faster than we might have worried.

Palantir gears up to expand its reach into UK's NHS, 2022. Financial Times. <https://on.ft.com/3xaqnszw>

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